

ORIGINS OF DAMAGE TOLERANCE IN POLYETHYLENE FIBER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This study concerns the analysis of high speed impact on flat panels of composites reinforced with ultra-strong PE fibers of Spectra type. More specifically, this study concerns the analysis of repeated impact indicating that through mechanical work these composites can become tougher and more penetration resistant. The origins of the unique damage tolerance of these composites, and of the work hardening that phenomena logically resembles the cold working of metals, lie in the intricate nano-scale composite structure of Spectra fibers and the nature of the crystalline phase of these fibers. The composite structure and properties of these fibers will be discussed in detail.

EXPERIMENTS AND ANALYSIS

The impact phenomena were investigated by high speed photography using a variety of projectiles and instrumented impact using Dynatup 8100 HST model. The composites were prepared using Spectra 1000 fibers embedded with Kraton matrix. The matrix content was ~30% by weight. The layers of unidirectional were than arranged in the orothropic [0/90] configuration.

Strain Rate Effects of Properties

Spectra fibers are viscoelastic, therefore, the properties are deformation rate dependent¹. The effects are very large and must be taken into consideration. In the event that a fast moving object is stopped by a panel, the deformation rates of the target can vary from the time of the contact to the time of arrest of the impacting object by 5 orders of magnitude.

The effective elastic moduli were predicted from the properties of its constituent components using micromechanics. Micromechanics was used to obtain the properties of unidirectional composite and the lamination theory to obtain the effective properties of multi-directional composites.

According to Halpin and Tsai² semiempirical model which is simple but widely applicable:

$$Q_c = \frac{Q_m(1 + \xi \chi \nu_f)}{1 - \chi \nu_f} \quad (1)$$

in which

$$\chi = \frac{Q_f - Q_m}{Q_f + \xi Q_m} \quad (2)$$

where Q represents the elastic moduli and ν is the volume fraction. ξ is regarded as the reinforcing factor which can be estimated from the geometrical structure of the composite or determined empirically. The subscripts c , m and f denote the composite, matrix and fiber, respectively.

In Table 1, the predicted properties of the Spectra® composite by this model are given.

Table 1. Effective Engineering Moduli of Unidirectional Spectra Composite Unit (Unit GPa)

Strain Rate (min. ⁻¹)	10	500	1000	5000	10000
Spectra 100 Fiber E_{xx}	101	130	145	221	268
Spectra Unidirectional Composite (Fiber 70% by wt/Kraton D1107)					
E_{xx}	70	91	101	154	188
E_{yy}	6.1	6.4	6.5	6.8	6.9
E_{zz}	6.1	6.4	6.5	6.8	6.9
G_{xy}	3.7	3.8	3.9	4.0	4.0

From these composite properties, three dimensional anisotropic moduli of Spectra® composite are obtained using the lamination theory. The constitutive relations of laminates can be expressed by

$$N_i = A_{ij} \epsilon_j + B_{ij} \kappa_j \quad (3)$$

where:

$$N_i = \frac{1}{h} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \sigma_i dz \quad (4)$$

$$A_{ij} = \frac{1}{h} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} Q_{ij} dz \quad (5)$$

$$B_{ij} = \frac{1}{h} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} Q_{ij} z dz \quad (6)$$

where σ_i and ε_j denote the stress of i th ply and mid-plane strains, respectively, and κ_j denote the curvatures of the plate. h is the thickness and z is the coordinate in the thickness direction. Q_{ij} is the elastic moduli of individual plies obtained using micromechanics, thus A_{ij} are the effective moduli of a multidirectional laminate. B_{ij} are called coupling stiffnesses and vanish for symmetric laminates, resulting in uncoupling of bending and stretching.

The effective engineering moduli (E_{ij} and G_{ij}) and Poisson's ratios (ν_{ij}) of a multi-directional laminate can be obtained from the above effective moduli by means of

$$E_{ii} = \frac{1}{a_{ii}}, \quad i=1,2,3 \quad (7)$$

$$G_{12} = \frac{1}{a_{66}}, \quad G_{23} = \frac{1}{a_{44}}, \quad G_{13} = \frac{1}{a_{55}} \quad (8)$$

$$\nu_{12} = -\frac{a_{12}}{a_{11}}, \quad \nu_{23} = -\frac{a_{23}}{a_{22}}, \quad \nu_{13} = -\frac{a_{13}}{a_{11}} \quad (9)$$

where a_{ij} is the inverse matrix of the stiffness matrix A_{ij} , i.e.,

$$a_{ij} = A_{ij}^{-1} \quad (10)$$

These effective engineering moduli are used for analyzing the behavior of laminated composite. Table 2 gives the engineering moduli of Spectra® composites.

Analysis of Ballistic Impact on Spectra® Composites

The ballistic impact analysis was carried out using the finite element analysis method. Since the ballistic impact phenomenon is a time dependent problem, the governing equation to be solved takes the following matrix differential equation form:

$$[M]\ddot{u} + [C]\dot{u} + [K]u = [F] \quad (11)$$

where $[M]$ is the mass matrix, $[C]$ damping matrix, $[K]$ stiffness matrix and $[F]$ external force matrix. u is the displacement vector. The upper dots denote differentiation with respect to time. This equation was solved using a general finite element computer program, Marc, developed by Marc Analysis Research Corporation. Detailed discussion regarding the solution method of the above dynamic equation is given by Zienkiewicz³

Table 2. Effective Engineering Moduli and Poisson's Ratio of [0/90] Spectra® Composite Unit (Unit GPa)

Strain Rate (min. ⁻¹)	10	500	1000	5000	10000
E _{xx}	38	49	54	81	98
E _{yy}	38	49	54	81	98
E _{zz}	6.3	6.6	6.7	7.0	7.1
G _{xy}	3.7	3.8	3.9	4.0	4.0
G _{yz}	3.7	3.8	3.9	4.0	4.0
G _{xx}	3.7	3.8	3.9	4.0	4.0
Poisson's Ratio					
V _{xy}	0.058	0.048	0.045	0.032	0.028
V _{yz}	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
V _{xz}	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3

In order to account for the strain rate dependent Spectra® fiber properties and the projectile penetration, the impact duration was divided into three steps, i.e., 0-35 microseconds, 35-70 microseconds and after 70 microseconds. Each time step, the strain rate was estimated from the iterative solution of the governing equation (Eq. 11).

With the set of properties listed in Tables 1 and 2, the analysis reproduced very well the deformations of the impacted panels and deceleration of various impactors. However, the same set of properties reproduced well only the first impact. When the impact was repeated and analyzed it was clear that the observed deflections and decelerations can no longer be matched using the same set of properties.

While this observation in itself is not surprising, the property changes indicated by the analysis were unique and totally unexpected. Instead of the expected weakening of the structure, the analysis indicated that on repeated impact the composite became tougher, more elastic and more penetration resistant.

Repeated Impact

To determine what happens in Spectra composites under severe impact and establish the cause of discrepancy between first and subsequent impacts we subjected a Spectra® panel that failed on first impact at ~ 66 (ft-lb) impact energy to repeated impacts starting with an impact energy of 57.0 (ft-lb).

On subsequent impacts the impact energy was gradually increased and reached on the fifth impact 80 (ft-lb) with no penetration. When on the sixth impact the penetration energy was finally increased to 95.4 (ft-lb) the panel failed. Hence, under the influence of repeated impact the penetration resistance of the panel increased from 66 to about 95 (lb-ft) or about 40%!

Maximum load on impactor recorded during these experiments (Fig. 1) showed that the stiffness of the panel increased as a result of repeated impact, and so did the energy at maximum load.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

It will be shown that in many respects, Spectra® polyethylene fibers are structurally in a class by themselves. As a consequence of polyethylene small repeating unit, chain flexibility, ability to undergo solid state transformation of the crystalline phase without breaking primary bonds, and its low glass transition temperature, PE fibers behave very differently from other strong organic polymers. Most importantly, Spectra® fibers have a unique composite structure in which nearly perfect crystals are covalently bonded to the surrounding matrix.

This unique composite structure in which the very strong crystals with high aspect ratio of 20 or more are covalently bonded to the surrounding rubbery amorphous matrix, is responsible for the damage tolerance and impact resistance of these fibers (Fig. 2). The incorporation of a finely dispersed rubbery phase in brittle thermoplastic and thermosets is a well known and widely used approach to improve the impact resistance of these systems. But the regularity of the Spectra rubbery and crystal phase structure has the characteristics of a macrolattice that gives rise to the small angle X-ray diffraction patterns from which the periodicities on 5 and 100 nm scale are discernible. This nanometer composite structure has its counterpart in nature, i.e., sea shells. Note that NACRE, which constitute the strong and impact resistant component of the sea shell, is made of very weak aragonite crystals bound by organic elastomeric matrix containing chitin⁴ is an example of how nature solves the problems of the damage tolerance that is essential for the survival of some species. In Spectra®, this Nacre, "brick and mortar", composite structure is replicated on approximately the same scale. However, in the case of Spectra®, the weak aragonite crystals are replaced with needle like, nearly perfect crystals of PE that in some respects (modulus in fiber direction) exhibit the properties of the diamond. Considering that these crystals probably also exhibit nearly theoretical strength of PE (that we place at 50 GPa or more), are covalently bonded to a rubbery matrix consisting of the same molecules and hence exhibiting a very strong adhesion, we see in PE fibers and composites an ideal structure to withstand high energy impact.

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Fig. 1 Maximum load during repetitive impact cycle.

Fig. 2 The Model of Cross-Sectional and Longitudinal Composite Structure of Spectra® Polyethylene Fibers